

Preanalytical considerations and out-patient vs in-patient tests of plasma metanephrines to diagnose pheochromocytoma

Georg Pommer,¹ Christina Pamporaki,² Mirko Peitzsch,³ Hanna Remde,⁴ Timo Deutschbein,^{4,5} Svenja Nölting,^{6,7} Lisa Marie Müller,⁶ Leah Braun,⁶ Sven Gruber,⁷ Alessio Pecori,⁸ Stephanie Hampson,⁹ Eleanor Davies,⁹ Anthony Stell,¹⁰ Gian Paolo Rossi,¹¹ Livia Lenzini,¹¹ Filippo Ceccato,¹¹ Henri J.L.M. Timmers,¹² Jaap Deinum,¹² Laurence Amar,^{13,14} Anne Blanchard,¹⁵ Stephanie Baron,¹⁶ Martin Fassnacht,⁴ Piotr Dobrowolski,¹⁷ Andrzej Januszewicz,¹⁷ Maria-Christina Zennaro,^{13,17} Aleksander Prejbisz,¹⁷ Graeme Eisenhofer^{2,3}

¹Institute of Clinical Genetics, ²Department of Internal Medicine III, ³Institute for Clinical Chemistry and Laboratory Medicine, University Hospital Carl Gustav Carus, Technische Universität Dresden, 01307 Dresden, Germany; ⁴Department of Internal Medicine I, University Hospital, University of Würzburg, 97082 Würzburg, Germany; ⁵Medicover Oldenburg MVZ, 26122 Oldenburg, Germany; ⁶Department of Medicine IV, University Hospital, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich, 80336 Munich, Germany; ⁷Department of Endocrinology, Diabetology and Clinical Nutrition, University Hospital Zurich and University of Zurich, CH-8091 Zurich, Switzerland; ⁸Department of Medical Sciences, University of Torino, 10126 Turin, Italy; ⁹Institute of Cardiovascular & Medical Sciences, University of Glasgow, G12 8TA Glasgow, United Kingdom; ¹⁰School of Computing and Information Systems, University of Melbourne, Melbourne, 3052 Victoria, Australia; ¹¹Department of Medicine-DIMED, University of Padua, 35128 Padua, Italy; ¹²Department of Internal Medicine, Radboud University Medical Centre, 6525 GA Nijmegen, The Netherlands; ¹³Inserm, PARCC, Université de Paris, 75012 Paris, France; ¹⁴Unité Hypertension artérielle - Centre de Reference en Maladies Rares des Surrénales, ¹⁵Centre d'Investigations Cliniques, ¹⁶Service de Physiologie, ¹⁷Service de Génétique, Assistance Publique-Hôpitaux de Paris, Hôpital Européen Georges Pompidou, 75015 Paris, France; ¹⁸Department of Hypertension, National Institute of Cardiology, 04-628 Warsaw, Poland.

Contents	Page
Supplemental results	2
Center-related differences in plasma metabolites in patients without PPGL.....	2
Supplemental table 1.....	2
Relationships of age with plasma metabolites.....	2
Supplemental figure 1.....	3
Plasma normetanephrine with and without PPGL.....	4
Supplemental figure 2.....	4
References.....	4

The data sets generated during and/or analyzed during the present study are publicly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6624878>.

Supplemental Results

Center-related differences in plasma metabolites in patients without PPGL

Plasma concentrations of normetanephrine were lowest in patients at WW, PA and NI, but for NI only for patients in the PMT protocol (Supplemental table 1). Patients studied at NI under the ENSAT-HT protocol, for which sampling conditions were different than under the PMT protocol (Table 1), showed higher ($P<0.05$) plasma concentrations of normetanephrine than all other centers except ZU. Plasma concentrations of metanephrine were also lower ($P<0.05$) for patients at NI in the PMT but not the ENSAT study. Similarly low plasma concentrations of metanephrine were observed for patients at PA and PD, as well as at MU in the ENSAT protocol. Plasma methoxytyramine showed complex differences among study centers that appeared to be in part protocol-related. Nevertheless, for patients studied in the PMT protocol, plasma concentrations of methoxytyramine were lowest for patients at WW and in the ENSAT protocol lowest at PA.

Supplemental Table 1. Plasma concentrations of normetanephrine (NMN), metanephrine (MN) and methoxytyramine (MTY) in patients without PPGL according to study center

Center	N	NMN (pg/mL)	MN (pg/mL)	MTY (pg/mL)
PMT				
DR	269	79 (75-83)	27 (26-29)	5.1 (4.8-5.4) ^g
MU	207	83 (79-89)	33 (30-35) ^e	6.2 (5.9-6.8) ^h
NI	99	68 (63-74) ^a	22 (20-24) ^f	6.5 (5.9-7.2) ^h
WU	246	86 (82-91)	29 (27-31)	5.2 (4.9-5.6) ^g
WW	975	56 (55-58) ^b	29 (28-30)	4.3 (4.1-4.4) ⁱ
ENSAT-HT				
GL	50	77 (68-87)	25 (21-28)	3.9 (3.4-4.6) ^j
MU*	118	75 (70-82)	19 (17-21) ^f	3.0 (2.7-3.3) ^k
NI*	134	101 (94-109) ^c	29 (27-32)	4.6 (4.2-5.0)
PA	478	62 (59-64) ^d	22 (21-23) ^f	2.8 (2.6-2.9) ^k
PD	125	87 (80-96)	23 (21-25) ^f	3.7 (3.4-4.1)
TU	141	82 (76-88)	30 (28-33)	3.3 (3.0-3.6)
ZU	27	75 (64-89)	31 (26-37)	3.6 (3.0-4.4)

Data are displayed as least square geometric means and confidence intervals. ^alower NMN than MU, WU and NI*; ^blower NMN than all other centers; ^chigher NMN than all other centers except ZU; ^dlower NMN than all other centers except WW, NI and ZU; ^ehigher MN than DR, NI, GL, PD, PA, NI and MU*; ^flower MN than DR, MU, WU, WW, NI*, TU and ZU; ^ghigher MTY than WW, PD, MU*, PA, TU and ZU; ^hhigher MTY than all other centers; ⁱhigher MTY than MU*, PA and TU; ^jhigher MTY than MU* and PA; ^klower MTY than DR, MU, NI, WU, WW, GL, and PD. All differences determined as $P<0.05$ by Tukey honestly significant difference test after least squares correction for age and sex.

Relationships of age with plasma metabolites

Divergent relationships of age with plasma normetanephrine and methoxytyramine, but not metanephrine, were observed in patients with and without PPGL (Supplemental figure 1). In agreement with previous reports (1-3), plasma concentrations of normetanephrine among patients without PPGL were positively related with age

Supplemental appendix

(Supplemental figure 1, panel A). Positive but relatively weak relationships were also observed between age and plasma concentrations of metanephrine and methoxytyramine (Supplemental figure 1, panels B & C). In contrast, for patients with PPGL there was a weak negative relationship of age with plasma normetanephrine and a trend for a negative relationship of age also with plasma methoxytyramine (Supplemental figure 1, panels D & F). Among patients with PPGLs, plasma metanephrine was positively related to age (Supplemental figure 1, panel E). For all patients with PPGLs relationships of plasma metabolites with age were at higher concentrations than in patients without PPGL.

Supplemental figure 1. Relationships of age with plasma concentrations of normetanephrine (A & D), metanephrine (B & E) and methoxytyramine (C & F) in patients without PPGL (A, B & C) and patients with PPGL (D, E & F). Note the logarithmic scales used to illustrate relationships among patients with PPGL.

Among patients without PPGL, the regression equations for relationships indicated that for every ten-year increase in age there would be respective 8, 1.1 and 0.4 pg/mL increases in plasma normetanephrine, metanephrine and methoxytyramine (Supplemental figure 1, panels A, B & C). Thus, the age-related increases in plasma metabolites are largest for plasma normetanephrine, with the regression equation indicating that a 65-year old adult patient can be expected to have twice as high plasma concentrations of normetanephrine than a 10-year old pediatric patient.

Plasma normetanephrine with and without PPGL

Plasma concentrations of normetanephrine as a ratio of age-specific upper cut-offs of reference intervals showed overlap between patients with and without PPGL (Supplemental figure 2). As expected, the overlap was larger according to 10%, 20% and 40% higher plasma concentrations of normetanephrine as might occur under different preanalytical conditions for blood draws and with consideration that the different preanalytical conditions were without effect in patients with PPGL (Table 3).

With a 10% increase in plasma concentrations of normetanephrine, as might be expected with cold compared to warm temperatures or sampling in semi-recumbent compared to fully recumbent positions, false positive rates increased from 5% to 7.2% (Supplemental figure 2).

With a 20% increase in plasma concentrations of normetanephrine, as might be expected for the combination of sampling in semi-recumbent compared to fully recumbent positions and cold rather than warmer temperatures, false positive rates doubled from 5% to 10.2%.

With a 40% increase in plasma concentrations of normetanephrine, as might be expected with sampling in an out-patient rather than an in-patient setting, false positive rates more than tripled from 5% to 17.3%.

Supplemental figure 2. Plasma concentrations of normetanephrine as a ratio of age-specific upper cut-offs of reference intervals in patients with and without PPGL. In patients without PPGL, ratios for plasma normetanephrine are shown according to 10% (+10%), 20% (+20%) and 40% (+40%) increases in concentrations. Expected false-positive rates (FPR) are shown according to those different concentrations.

References

1. Eisenhofer G, Friberg P, Pacak K, Goldstein DS, Murphy DL, Tsigos C, et al. Plasma metadrenalines: do they provide useful information about sympatho-adrenal function and catecholamine metabolism? *Clin Sci (Lond)*. 1995;88(5):533-542.
2. Sawka AM, Thabane L, Gafni A, Levine M, Young WF, Jr. Measurement of fractionated plasma metanephrines for exclusion of pheochromocytoma: Can specificity be improved by adjustment for age? *BMC Endocr Disord*. 2005;5(1):1.
3. Eisenhofer G, Lattke P, Herberg M, Siegert G, Qin N, Darr R, et al. Reference intervals for plasma free metanephrines with an age adjustment for normetanephrine for optimized laboratory testing of pheochromocytoma. *Ann Clin Biochem*. 2013;50(Pt 1):62-69.